

Social Movements and the Diffusion of Tactics and Repertoires: Activists' Network in Anti-Globalism Movement

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Abstract : Non-Government Organizations (NGOs), Non-Profit Organizations (NPOs), Social Enterprises and other actors play an important role in political decisions in governments at the international levels. Especially, such organizations' and activists' network in civil society is quite important to effect to the global politics. To solve the complex social problems in global era, diverse actors should cooperate each other. Moreover, network of protesters is also contributes to diffuse tactics, information and other resources of social movements. Based on the findings from the study of International Trade Fairs (ITFs), the author analyzes the network of activists in anti-globalism movement. This research focuses the transition of 54 activists' whole network in the "protest event" against 2008 G8 summit in Japan. Their network is examined at the three periods: Before protest event phase, during protest event phase and after event phase. A mixed method is used in this study: the author shows the hypothesis from social network analysis and evaluates that with interview data analysis. This analysis gives the two results. Firstly, the more protesters participate to the various events during the protest event, the more they build the network. After that, active protesters keep their network as well. From interview data, we can understand that the active protesters can build their network and diffuse the information because they communicate with other participants and understand that diverse issues are related. This paper comes to same conclusion with previous researches: protest events activate the network among the political activists. However, some participants succeed to build their network, others do not. "Networked" activists are participated in the various events for short period of time and encourage the diffusion of information and tactics of social movements.

Keywords : social movement, global justice movement, tactics, diffusion

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